

Herbicide use and occurrence of *Echinochloa* spp. in ricefields in dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka

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This ricefield weed survey included 251 fields in the dry and intermediate rice growing zones of Sri Lanka in 1994 and 1995. All species within 5- × 5-m plots were identified and farmers interviewed about practices. During the 1994 maha season (northeastern monsoon, October-December), we identified 132 different weeds belonging to 32 families in 176 fields. During the 1995 yala season (southwestern monsoon, April-August), 96 different weeds belonging to 21 different families were identified in 75 fields. In both seasons, *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link and *E. crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv. (Poaceae) ranked among the 10 most important weed

Table 1. Frequency of *Echinochloa* spp. during the 1994-95 survey in the dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka.

Weed	Frequency (%)	
	Maha season	Yala season
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	52.3	81.3
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	36.9	57.3
<i>Echinochloa frumentacea</i> Link	13.1	21.3
<i>Echinochloa stagnina</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv.	6.8	13.3

species, while *E. frumentacea* Link and *E. stagnina* (Retz.) P. Beauv. occurred less frequently. Overall, *Echinochloa* spp. frequencies were higher during the dry yala season (Table 1). The reason for this might be that during the yala season all cultivated rice is irrigated whereas during the rainy season (maha) upland rice is also grown. Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA), often used in ecological vegetation science, conducted on species occurring in more than three fields, revealed that during maha, *E. crus-galli*

is a typical species in frequently irrigated ricefields, whereas *E. colona* occurs as well under drier regimes. Water level in ricefields during yala, however, does not seem to have a significant influence on their distribution.

From interviews with the farmers, it became clear that the range of herbicides used is very limited. Propanil, active against several grassy and broadleaf weeds, and MCPA, against broadleaves, are the most frequently applied herbicides. Only about a third of the farmers reported using the recommended amounts of herbicides (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Herbicide use (% of farmers interviewed) in ricefields during the 1994-95 survey in the dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka.

Class ^a	Propanil	MCPA
I	41.7	37.5
II	20.8	30.6
III	37.5	31.9

^a Class I: no application; class II: amount of herbicide applied is less than recommended; class III: recommended amounts according to the Department of Agriculture.

Integrated weed management through smother intercrops in rainfed lowland rice

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Among the management options in the first 40-50 d of rainfed lowland rice, smother crops can ensure effective weed control. We evaluated the weed-smothering effect of green manure, including *Crotalaria juncea*, *Vigna sinensis*, *Glycine max*, *Sesbania rostrata*, and *S. aculeata* during 1992 and 1994 at the ARS, Mugad, Karnataka, India.

The crop treatments were combined factorially with either hand weeding (HW) alone at 30 d after rice emergence (DE) or with intercultivation (IC) at 15 DE followed by hand weeding at 40

DE. Weed-free check, weedy check, and farmer's practices were included for comparison (see table). The rice and green manure seeds were mixed in a

100:25 kg ha⁻¹ proportion and sown in 20-cm rows by seed drill in semidry soil at the onset of the monsoon season. Green manures were buried in stand-

Grain yield and weed dry weight in rainfed lowland rice as influenced by integrated weed management involving smother crops. Karnataka, India. 1992 and 1994.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	
	1992	1994	1992	1994
<i>C. juncea</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.2	5.9	175	78
<i>C. juncea</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.2	6.1	50	49
<i>V. sinensis</i> + HW at 30 DE	6.3	5.8	103	89
<i>V. sinensis</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.7	6.8	25	49
<i>G. max</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.3	5.9	58	137
<i>G. max</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.9	7.2	45	69
<i>S. rostrata</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.9	5.8	106	90
<i>S. rostrata</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.1	5.9	53	53
<i>S. aculeata</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.3	4.6	181	124
<i>S. aculeata</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.7	5.2	36	100
Weed-free check	6.6	6.6	111	8
Weedy check	3.2	2.7	361	461
Farmer's practice	6.8	6.7	81	40
Butachlor + HW at 30 DE	6.5	6.7	95	49
LSD (0.05)	1	1.2		42

^aHW = hand weeding; DE = days after rice emergence; IC = intercultivation.

ing water at 40 DE by wet IC and followed by passing a wooden plank between crop rows. A randomized complete block design with three replications was used. Rainfall amounted to 1150 and 1135 mm in 75 and 79 rainy days during the cropping seasons of 1992 and 1994, respectively. The rice cultivar was Abhilash (155 d). Common weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* spp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyanotis* spp., and *Eclipta prostrata*.

The results (see table) indicated that intercropped *C. juncea*, *V. sinensis*, *G. max*, and *S. rostrata*, when combined with 1 IC at 15 DE and 1 HW at 40 DE, could suppress weeds effectively. The rice yields obtained in these plots were similar to those recorded after butachlor applications with 1 HW at 30 DE (see table), suggesting that these crops could replace butachlor application when combined with 1 IC. *Sesbania aculeata*, which grows very slowly, could not suppress weeds effectively.

Vigna sinensis had better weed-smothering ability and rice yields were comparable with those using butachlor with 1 HW at 30 DE, even when combined with 1 HW at 30 DE.

Apart from their weed-smothering ability these legumes can fix atmospheric N and add a considerable amount of organic matter to the soil. Therefore, intercropping of *C. juncea*, *V. sinensis*, *G. max*, and *S. rostrata* may be encouraged for sustainable weed management in rainfed lowland rice. ■

Research methodology

Modified method for determination of amylose content using a single rice kernel

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Amylose content determines the stickiness and eating quality of cooked rice. We modified Shen's (1990) method to determine amylose content in a single rice kernel. We tested the method by analyzing 11 varieties having waxy, intermediate, and high amylose content.

The final protocol involved the following steps. A single rice kernel was milled by a hand-set miller and the embryo carefully removed with a blade. The material was weighed on an Afcoset electronic balance (0.1 mg-180 g) and placed in a 50-mL graduated tube. A total of 0.1 mL of 95% ethanol and 1.8 mL of 1 N NaOH solution was added. The mixture was kept in a hot-water bath (35 °C) for 20 h. It was shaken well and brought to 20 ml with distilled water. A 5 mL aliquot was pipetted into a 100 mL volumetric flask. One milliliter of acetic acid and 2 mL of iodine solution were added. The solution was brought to full volume with distilled water and shaken well. Color was read at 620 nm after 20 min in a UV

Amylose content of 11 varieties tested by two methods. Cuttack, India.

Genotype	Modified		Juliano	
	Amylose content	Type	Amylose content	Type
Malagkit Sungsong	3.5	Waxy	3.7	Waxy
Basmati 370	19.9	Intermediate	19.0	Intermediate
Karnal local	20.8	Intermediate	20.1	Intermediate
Basmati 113	20.8	Intermediate	20.1	Intermediate
T412	21.3	Intermediate	20.8	Intermediate
Pakistan Basmati	21.4	Intermediate	20.7	Intermediate
Sitabhog	21.4	Intermediate	20.9	Intermediate
Tulsimanjari	23.7	High	23.9	High
Savitri	24.7	High	24.9	High
Gayatri	25.2	High	26.3	High
Ratna	25.2	High	25.5	High

1201 spectrophotometer. Concentration of amylose was determined from a standard curve using amylose (Sigma).

According to the amylose content of control varieties Malagkit Sungsong (waxy), Basmati 370 (intermediate), and Ratna (high), we changed the classification of amylose to waxy (0-5), intermediate (5-17), intermediate (17-22), and high (>22). The amylose content of the 11 varieties is shown in the table. Most of them were intermediate, four were high, and one was waxy.

This method is suitable for determination of amylose content in a large number of samples for genetic studies. The results agreed closely with those obtained using Juliano's standard method. ■

Comparison of two scoring systems for evaluating stem rot resistance in rice, and a new proposed rating scale

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Genotypes judged susceptible by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES, 1988) often fall into the resistant or intermediate category when scored using the rating scale by Jackson et al (1977). The SES scale is based on disease incidence (% infected tillers) and excludes few resistant genotypes.